

Deliverable 7.1

Project Management Handbook

UK participants in Horizon Europe Project PHOEBE are supported by UKRI grant numbers 10038897 (The International Road Assessment Programme – iRAP) and 10056912 (The Flow)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101076963

The sole responsibility for the content of this document lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. Neither CINEA nor the European Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Document Control Page

Deliverable number	7.1
Deliverable title	<i>Project Management Handbook</i>
Deliverable version	1.1
Work Package number	7
Work Package Title	<i>Project Coordination and Management</i>
Due date of delivery	30/11/2022
Actual date of delivery	30/11/2022
Dissemination level	<i>Public (PU)</i>
Type	<i>Document, report ®</i>
Editor(s)	<i>Alenka Volk (EIRA)</i>
Contributor(s)	<i>Sam Chapman (FLOOW), Mark Burke (FLOOW), Shanna Luchesi (iRAP), Niklas Schmalholz (POLIS), Andréia Lopes Azevedo (POLIS)</i>
Reviewer(s)	<i>Niklas Schmalholz (POLIS), Shanna Luchesi (iRAP)</i>
Project name	<i>Predictive Approaches for Safer Urban Environments</i>
Project Acronym	<i>PHOEBE</i>
Project starting date	01/11/2022
Project duration	<i>45 months</i>
Rights	<i>PHOEBE consortium</i>

PM efforts per beneficiary that contributed to the deliverable

#	Partner	PM effort in the Deliverable
1	EIRA	0.14
2	iRAP	0.11
3	POLIS	0.15
4	FLOOW	0.1
Total	<i>PHOEBE Consortium</i>	0.5

Document History

Version	Date	Beneficiary	Description
0.1	9/11/2022	Alenka Volk (EIRA)	Initial Draft
0.2	21/11/2022	Sam Chapman (FLOOW) Mark Burke (FLOOW) Shanna Luchesi (iRAP) Niklas Schmalholz (POLIS) Andréia Lopes Azevedo (POLIS)	Revisions and inputs: FLOOW: general revisions and suggestions, adding references regarding UKRI POLIS: general revision and suggestions, adding information in the Chapters 7 and 8 iRAP: general revisions and suggestions, adding Quality Management Plan, Chapter 9
0.3	25/11/2022	Alenka Volk (EIRA)	Preliminary Final Document integrating partners contribution
0.4	28/11/2022	Niklas Schmalholz (POLIS) Andréia Lopes Azevedo (POLIS)	Proof reading and general revision
0.5	29/11/2022	Shanna Luchesi (iRAP)	Final review
1.0	30/11/2022	Alenka Volk (EIRA)	Final document
1.1	30/3/2023	Alenka Volk (EIRA)	Change to the new Phoebe deliverable template, change in Figure 1 and Table 1 (WP7 leader update), correction in Table 8 (mailing list address update, naming of e-mail addresses corrected)

Project Executive Summary

Safer urban environments are needed for all road users to ensure that the European Union's meet the targets to halve road deaths and injuries by 2030. Vulnerable road users require specific attention in an urban environment that is subject to constant change as new forms of transport and micro-mobility enter the system. Existing traffic simulation models allow changes in traffic conditions to be tested. However, such systems tend to be geared towards increasing the vehicle throughput or decreasing travel time rather than evaluating outcomes specific to vulnerable road users and road safety. Furthermore, city administrations and transport managers lack predictive tools that allow them to model the effect of implications of a given set of mitigations in terms of road safety, mobility and sustainable transport. Such tools would help to support the associated policy, regulatory and consumer response.

This project, Predictive Approaches for Safer Urban Environments, (PHOEBE), will move beyond the state of the art and deliver an interdisciplinary solution that will integrate traffic simulation, road safety assessment, the effects of human behaviour, modal shift, induced demand modelling, and emerging mobility data into a harmonised assessment framework for road safety. The PHOEBE framework, software module and knowledge products will allow for a dynamic safety prediction and socioeconomic evaluation that is evidence-based and simulates future scenarios and impacts.

Simple and effective visualisation of socioeconomic modelling will provide confidence for policy decisions and investment. City administrations across the EU will be consulted as the PHOEBE framework is developed and deployed. The capability of the framework to achieve positive outcomes will be demonstrated in three distinct areas; the cities of Athens (Greece), Valencia (Spain), and the combined authority region of the West Midlands (United Kingdom). These areas were selected to safeguard a diversity of urban areas in which extensive traffic modelling has already taken place. This diversity should ensure that our solutions are scalable and can be used to assess the effect of traffic mitigation on safety for a large number of urban environments after the project ends. Achieving the expected objectives requires commitment and dedication from all project partners.

This document contains instructions concerning the project procedures and other useful information to be used during the project's lifetime. However, it is important to note that this manual does not constitute a legally binding document, so if discrepancies between the signed Grant Agreement and its Annexes, the Consortium Agreement and this handbook should occur, the official signed documents prevail.

PHOEBE pilot cities

List of participating cities:

- Athens (Greece)
- Valencia (Spain)
- West Midlands (United Kingdom)

Social Links:

 https://twitter.com/Project_PHOEBE

 <https://www.linkedin.com/company/phoebe-project/>

 <https://www.youtube.com/@phoebeproject>

For further information please visit WWW.PHOEBE-PROJECT.EU

Project Partners

Organisation	Country	Abbreviation
EVROPSKI INSTITUT ZA OCENJEVANJE CEST - EURORAP	SI	EIRA
ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	EL	NTUA
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT	NL	TUD
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	DE	TUM
AIMSUN SLU	ES	AIM
POLIS AISBL	BE	POLIS
FACTUAL CONSULTING SL	ES	FC
UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA	ES	UPV
OSEVEN SINGLE MEMBER PRIVATE COMPANY	EL	O7
THE FLOW LIMITED	UK	FLOW
INTERNATIONAL ROAD ASSESSMENT PROGRAMME	UK	iRAP

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
SC	The Steering Committee
PC	The Project Coordinator
PP	Project Partner
WP Leaders	Work package leaders
TC	The Technical Committee
EB	The Ethical Board
DM	The Dissemination manager
WPs	Work Packages
EC	European Comission
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation

Table of Contents

Contents

Project Executive Summary	3
PHOEBE pilot cities	3
Project Partners	4
List of abbreviations and acronyms	5
Deliverable executive summary	8
Progress beyond the state of the art and play	8
1 Project Organisation.....	9
1.1 Governance Structure	9
1.2 Plan of meetings	12
2 Participating institutions and persons	13
3 Management process.....	16
3.1 Reporting process	16
4 Eligibility of cost.....	18
4.1 General conditions	18
4.2 Specific conditions	18
4.3 Ineligible costs.....	19
4.4 Reporting periods.....	19
4.5 Deadlines for Periodic Reporting	19
4.6 Files naming	20
4.7 Deliverable preparation procedure.....	20
5 Instructions for exploitation and dissemination	21
5.1 Internal dissemination	21
5.2 Active Accounts.....	22
5.3 Internal communication channels.....	22
5.4 PHOEBE mailing lists.....	22
5.5 External dissemination	23
5.5.1 Public website	23
5.5.2 PHOEBE logo.....	23
5.5.3 PHOEBE e-leaflet.....	23
5.5.4 Publication policy.....	23
5.6 Confidentiality procedure	23
6 Format Specifications for the digital documents and media	24
6.1 Text documents.....	24
6.2 Presentations	24
6.3 Tables.....	24

6.4	Images.....	24
6.5	Video	25
7	Quality Assurance Plan	25
7.1	Peer review	25
7.1.1	Format and presentation	25
7.1.2	Content.....	25
7.1.3	Accordance with project objectives and goals	25
8	Annex	27
	List of Deliverables	27
	List of Milestones	28

List of figures

Figure 1	Phoebe governance structure.....	9
----------	----------------------------------	---

List of tables

Table 1	WP leaders.....	10
Table 2	Steering Committee Members	11
Table 3	Meeting Matrix.....	12
Table 4	timeline of the SC and consortium meetings	13
Table 5	List of participating institutions and persons	16
Table 6	Periodic reporting deadlines	20
Table 7	Naming of files	20
Table 8	Current PHOEBE mailing lists	22

Deliverable executive summary

The Project Management Handbook is an important document that comprises instructions regarding the project procedures and other useful information to be applied during the project's lifetime. This handbook represents deliverable 7.1, which is related to WP7, Task 7.2 'Project management and quality assurance' that combines all the activities to be implemented to ensure good project management.

The handbook includes official information about the project contract, the description of the project organisation (governance structure, Project Coordinator, Technical Committee, Steering Committee, and others), a summary of the preliminary plan of meetings of the PHOEBE Consortium during the whole duration of the project and a complete list of participating institutions and persons involved in the PHOEBE Project. By containing all this information, the handbook is envisioned as support to beneficiaries and associated partners, but also as a useful management tool for the project coordinator.

Based on this, the following parts of the handbook describe the management procedures concerning the reporting process, periods and writing, the instructions for internal and external dissemination and exploitation process, as well as the quality assurance. The handbook also encourages unproblematic relations between the partners involved, by setting out an operational framework for the project. Therefore, the information reported in D7.1 represents project management guidelines, which define the organisational structure, key role persons with specific responsibilities, deadlines for review meetings, deliverables, and milestones. Additionally, D7.1 reports useful information for achieving the results of PHOEBE, specifying the right procedures to follow in terms of reporting documents, eligibility of costs, instructions for dissemination, and format specifications for digital documents and media.

Progress beyond the state of the art and play

This chapter focuses on the organisational structure of the PHOEBE consortium.

Since PHOEBE involves 11 partners from 7 different countries, a clear allocation of roles and responsibilities across the consortium is mandatory. Thus, a Steering Committee and a Technical Committee of the project were set up, and a list of key persons from different partners were appointed to fill a specific role according to their own expertise (e.g., technical, dissemination, exploitation). In addition, several mailing lists, which will be updated regularly, were set up to foster agile communication management regarding specific topics and/or work packages.

In addition to allowing the Steering Committee to easily handle the project's progress at all levels, this approach is fundamental to facilitate the coordination, discussion and dissemination at national and global levels. PHOEBE shall demonstrate the feasibility of defining safety assessment framework. Particularly, the impact of the project should be assessed through specific key performance indicators at the European level, promoting the sustainability of the PHOEBE solution widely beyond the end of the project.

1 Project Organisation

1.1 Governance Structure

The PHOEBE Consortium is organised in a detailed structure to ensure the smooth management and quality assurance of the activities (Figure 1). This structure shall ensure appropriate communication within the partnership.

Figure 1 Phoebe governance structure

The governance structure of the consortium shall comprise the following Consortium Bodies:

The Steering Committee (SC) is the decision-making body of the consortium in which all 11 partners are represented.

The Project Coordinator (PC) is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The Project Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Beneficiary, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

Work Package leaders

The PHOEBE activities are broken down into Work Packages (WPs) in order to ensure adequate execution and coordination of tasks within the foreseen time frame and budget. Each work package will be under the responsibility of one consortium partner, named Work Package leader (WP leader), which is obligated to control the performed work of the WP (see Table 1).

WPs	WP Leader	Organization
WP1	Eleonora Papadimitriou	TUD
WP2	Sam Chapman	FLOW
WP3	James Bradford	iRAP
WP4	Marko Ševrović	EIRA
WP5	George Yannis	NTUA
WP6	Andreia Lopes Azevedo	POLIS
WP7	Shona Holroyd	EIRA

Table 1 WP leaders

WP Leaders will be in charge of leading technical progress and control of the WP, in order to ensure that WP goals are met on time and within budget restrictions and of reporting research progress to the Steering Committee and Project Coordinator regularly. This will cover establishing monthly WP-level meetings and monitoring the technical progress, results, deliverables and compliance with the Work Programme. The WPs leaders will also be responsible for the timely submission of the deliverables resulting from their work packages and for providing the required reporting to ensure efficient overall monitoring and coordination. The Project Coordinator will summarise overall project progress, updating planning charts and human resources records.

The Technical Committee (TC, formed by WP leaders) coordinates among WPs and solves possible deviations. This committee is led by the Technical Manager, who monitors the technical activities of the project and reports to the Steering Committee any unexpected delay, obstacle, deviation or inability to achieve results planned in each WP task.

The Ethical Board (EB) is composed of consortium partners for the revision, approval, and application of the legal and ethical requirements and ensuring compliance with the guidelines defined in the Ethical Manual. This body is led by the Ethics Board Manager, who is responsible for promoting that the activities implemented within the project comply with the ethical guidance from WP7; and for solving any ethical issues which might be raised during the implementation of the project.

The Dissemination manager (DM) leads and coordinates the communication and interactions with external bodies and stakeholders in order to achieve the highest possible impact and benefits for the project.

The Partner Organisations

The Partner Organisations represent the management of each individual partner within the project. Individual partner leaders provide feedback to their management as necessary, and the coordinating partners shall also provide feedback to them as applicable.

Each full project partner allocates a single contact person for the project, who has the authority to both represent and commit their organisation in the project’s decision-making process or in case of a conflict resolution. The partner representative undertakes support and administrative responsibilities of their organisation regarding submissions of cost statements and deliverables or other administrative information requested by the Project Officer. As such, they report information and issues to both the Coordinator and represent the Partner in the Steering Committee.

Project Partner	SC Member
EIRA	Marko Ševrovic
NTUA	George Yannis
TUD	Eleonora Papadimitriou
TUM	Constantinos Antoniou
AIM	Mark Brackstone
POLIS	Ivo Cré
FC	Stefania Pesavento
UPV	Ana María Pérez-Zuriaga
O7	Petros Fortsakis
FLOOW	Sam Chapman
iRAP	James Bradford

Table 2 Steering Committee Members

The Task Leaders

The diversity of activities undertaken in the WPs mandates the delegation of coordination responsibilities to the Task Leaders. The Task Leaders report directly to the WP Leader. They are briefed about the higher-level requirements of the task they are leading and are required to steer the activities towards timely completion. When needed, the Task Leaders can also report the synthesis of these activities to the Project Coordinator.

External expert Sounding board (SB)

A small group of stakeholders (max. 10) will be established through POLIS to act as a sounding board for project work in progress and findings, to serve as a platform for promoting the take up of PHOEBE outputs. The group will be made up primarily of potential end users of PHOEBE contributions. It will include road safety practitioners, mobility and modelling experts, among others. An open call for applications will be done at the beginning of the project, and due consideration will be given to gender, diversity and geographical representation.

In order to organise the activities of the group and ensure the necessary confidentiality conditions, POLIS will define the Terms of Reference for the group that will be confirmed with the consortium and agreed upon by the group’s members.

1.2 Plan of meetings

Table 3 summarises the type and frequency of progress meetings, review meetings, SC meetings and other relevant meetings, which different partners will host.

Meeting Type	Materials kept	Participants	Chair	Frequency	Format
Consortium meetings	Meeting minutes List of presence or recording	All partners	Coordinator	Twice a year	In person or online
Technical meetings	Meeting minutes List of presence or recording	Technical Committee	Technical Manager	Monthly	In person or online
WP meetings	Short notes Recording	WP leader and task leaders	WP Leaders	Monthly	Online
Steering committee meetings	Meeting minutes List of presence or recording	Steering committee members	Coordinator	Quarterly	Online or in person
Integration with projects that have been awarded by the EC	Minutes List of presence or recording	Project Coordinator and WP leaders	Coordinator	Quarterly	Online
Sounding Board meeting	List of presence or recording	SE Members and Technical Committee	Technical Manager	At least yearly	Online or in person

Table 3 Meeting Matrix

In the Table 4 there is a provisional timeline of SC meetings and Consortium meetings.

Year	2022	2023				2024				2025				2026		
Quarter	IV	I	II	III	IV	I	II	III	IV	I	II	III	IV	I	II	III
SC meetings	Dec	Mar	Jun	Sept	Dec	Mar	Jun	Sept	Dec	Mar	Jun	Sept	Dec	Mar	Jun	
Consortium Meetings	Dec		Jun		Dec		Jun		Dec		Jun		Dec		Jun	

Table 4 Timeline of the SC and consortium meetings

2 Participating institutions and persons

The up to date list of participant contacts is available on the reserved area of the repository system on Google Drive: <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1yZHzdWvOY5dlO9Vr74n4CwR6dK6Cbtyh>

Important note:

Each partner leader must inform administrators of the mailing for updates in case any contact from the partners leaves the project for any reason (the person leaves the institution or is going to work on another project) or a new person joins the team.

The following Table 5 summarises the current list:

Name and surname	PP	Contact e-mail
Monica Olyslagers	iRAP	monica.olyslagers@irap.org
Shanna Lucchesi	iRAP	shanna.lucchesi@irap.org
Shona Holroyd	iRAP	shona.holroyd@irap.org
James Bradford	iRAP	james.bradford@irap.org
Helen Noble	iRAP	helen.noble@irap.org

Name and surname	PP	Contact e-mail
Judy Williams	iRAP	Judy.williams@irap.org
Mark Brackstone	Aimsun	mark.brackstone@aimsun.com
Jordi Casas	Aimsun	jordi.casas@aimsun.com
Marcel Sala	Aimsun	marcel.sala@aimsun.com
Sam Chapman	The Floop	sam@thefloop.com
Mark Burke	The Floop	mark.burke@thefloop.com
Stefania Pesavento	Factual	stefania@factual-consulting.com
Marc Figuls	Factual	marc@factual-consulting.com
Ivo Cre	Polis Network	icre@polisnetwork.eu
Julie Lucca	Polis Network	jlucca@polisnetwork.eu
Andréia Lopes Azevedo	Polis Network	alopes@polisnetwork.eu
Marina Bezier	POLIS Network	mbezier@polisnetwork.eu
Niklas Schmalholz	Polis Network	nschmalholz@polisnetwork.eu
Eleonora Papadimitriou	TU Delft	e.papadimitriou@tudelft.nl

Name and surname	PP	Contact e-mail
Amir Pooyan Afghari	TU Delft	a.p.afghari-1@tudelft.nl
Olivera Rozi	EIRA	olivera.rozi@eurorap.org
Marko Sevrovic	EIRA	marko.sevrovic@eira-si.eu
Alenka Volk	EIRA	alenka.volk@eira-si.eu
Suzy Charman	RSF (UK)	suzy.charman@roadsafetyfoundation.org
George Yannis	NTUA	geyannis@central.ntua.gr
Eleni I. Vlahogianni	NTUA	elenivl@mail.ntua.gr
Apostolos Ziakopoulos	NTUA	apziak@central.ntua.gr
Maria Oikonomou	NTUA	moikonomou@mail.ntua.gr
Areti Gouma	NTUA	agouma@central.ntua.gr
Constantinos Antoniou	TUM	c.antoniou@tum.de
Mohamed Abouelela	TUM	mohamed.abouelela@tum.de
Christelle Al Haddad	TUM	christelle.haddad@tum.de
Petros Fortsakis	OSeven	pfortsakis@oseven.io

Name and surname	PP	Contact e-mail
Alexis Aivaliotis	OSeven	aaivaliotis@oseven.io
Elina Frantzola	OSeven	efrantzola@oseven.io
Ana María Pérez Zuriga	UPV	anpezu@tra.upv.es
Alfredo García	UPV	agarciag@tra.upv.es
Francisco Javier Camacho Torregrosa	UPV	fracator@tra.upv.es
Griselda López Maldonado	UPV	grilomal@tra.upv.es
David Llopis Castelló	UPV	dallocas@upv.es
SGL_europeos	UPV	sgi-europeos@upv.es

Table 5 List of participating institutions and persons

3 Management process

3.1 Reporting process

During the project, each Partner should contribute to:

- **reporting** (see article 21.1 of the Grant Agreement) on the progress of the action (e.g. deliverables, milestones, outputs/outcomes, potential risks or other indicators), in the Portal Continuous Reporting tool in accordance with the timing and conditions it sets out (as agreed with the granting authority).

Standardised deliverables (e.g. progress reports not linked to payments, reports on cumulative expenditure, special reports, etc., if any) must be submitted using the templates published on the Portal.

- **periodic reporting** within 60 days following the end of each reporting period (including the last reporting period). The reporting periods are defined in the Data Sheet of the Grant Agreement and

are listed in the following section. According to Article 21.2 of the Grant Agreement, the periodic reports comprise:

- **periodic technical report** contains an overview of the action implementation. The layout of the template must be followed, which includes:
 - i. an explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and an overview of the progress of work towards the objectives of the actions, including achievements and attainment of any milestones and deliverables identified in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement. When needed, this report should include the justification for the differences between the work expected to be carried out in accordance with Annex 1 and the one actually performed. The report must detail impact, exploitation and dissemination of the results as well as the communication activities;
 - ii. a summary for publication by the Commission;
 - iii. the answers to the Horizon Europe questionnaire, covering issues related to the action implementation and the economic and societal impact, notably in the context of the Horizon Europe key performance indicators and the Horizon Europe monitoring requirements.
- **periodic financial report** containing the eligible costs and contributions for each budget category and, for the final payment, also the revenues for the action (see Articles 6 and 22 of the Grant Agreement). It consists of:
 - i. an individual financial statement (see Annex 4 of the Grant Agreement) from each beneficiary and from each linked third party (if relevant), for the reporting period concerned. The individual financial statement must detail the eligible costs (actual costs, unit costs and flat-rate costs; see Article 6 of the GA) for each budget category (see Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement). The beneficiaries and linked third parties (if relevant) must declare all eligible costs, even if — for actual costs, unit costs and flat rate costs — they exceed the amounts indicated in the estimated budget (see Annex 2 of the grant agreement). Amounts which are not declared in the individual financial statement will not be taken into account by the Commission. If an individual financial statement is not submitted for a reporting period, it may be included in the periodic financial report for the next reporting period.

Each beneficiary and each linked third party (if applicable) must certify that:

- the information provided is full, reliable and true;
- the costs declared are eligible as described in Article 6 ‘Eligibility and ineligible costs and contributions’ of the Grant Agreement;
- the costs can be substantiated by adequate records and supporting documentation (Article 20 ‘Record-keeping’) that will be produced upon request (Article 21 ‘Reporting’) or in the context of checks, reviews, audits and investigations (Article 25 ‘Checks, reviews, audits and investigations’);
- ii. an explanation of the use of resources and the information on subcontracting (see Article 9.3 of the Grant Agreement) from each beneficiary and from each linked third party, for the reporting period concerned;
- iii. a **periodic financial statement**, created automatically by the electronic exchange system, consolidating the individual financial statements for the reporting period

concerned and including — except for the last reporting period — the request for interim payment.

The consortium shall transmit the reports and other deliverables through the Project Coordinator to the Commission by electronic means. All reports and deliverables shall be in English.

4 Eligibility of cost

4.1 General conditions

According to Article 6 of the GA, eligible costs can be divided into: actual costs, unit costs and flat-rate costs.

To be eligible, **actual costs** must be:

- actually incurred by the beneficiary;
- incurred in the period set out in Article 4, with the exception of costs relating to the submission of the final periodic report, which may be incurred afterwards (see Article 21);
- declared under one of the budget categories set out in Article 6.2 and Annex 2;
- incurred in connection with the action as described in Annex 1 and necessary for its implementation;
- identifiable and verifiable, in particular recorded in the beneficiary's accounts in accordance with the accounting standards applicable in the country where the beneficiary is established and with the beneficiary's usual cost accounting practices;
- comply with the applicable national law on taxes, labour and social security;
- reasonable, justified and must comply with the principle of sound financial management, in particular regarding economy and efficiency.

To be eligible, **unit costs** (if any) must be declared under one of the budget categories set out in Article 6.2 and Annex 2. The units must be:

- actually used or produced by the beneficiary in the period set out in Article 4 (with the exception of units relating to the submission of the final periodic report, which may be used or produced afterwards; see Article 21);
- necessary for implementing the action or produced by it.

Moreover, the number of units must be identifiable and verifiable, in particular supported by records and documentation (see Article 20).

To be eligible, flat-rate costs must be calculated by applying the flat-rate set out in Annex 2. Furthermore, the costs to which the flat-rate is applied must comply with the conditions for eligibility (see Article 6).

4.2 Specific conditions

Additionally, to the general conditions, costs to be eligible must also satisfy specific requirements according to the category in which they are declared: direct personnel costs, direct costs of subcontracting, other direct costs, and indirect costs. Direct costs are expenses that are directly linked to the action implementation and can therefore be attributed to it directly, whereas indirect costs are not directly linked to the action implementation and, therefore, cannot be attributed directly to it.

Direct costs include:

- personnel costs, according to the conditions defined in Article 6.2 point A;
- Subcontracting costs, including related duties, taxes and charges such as non-deductible value added tax (VAT) paid by the beneficiary, according to the criteria in Article 6.2 point B;
- Purchase costs according to the conditions defined in Article 6.2 point C: travel and subsistence costs; equipment, other goods, works and services.

Indirect costs are eligible if they are declared on the basis of the flat-rate of 25% of the eligible direct costs (see Article 6.2 point E), excepting for:

- volunteers costs;
- subcontracting costs;
- financial support to third parties;
- exempted specific cost categories, if any.

4.3 Ineligible costs

Costs are considered not eligible if they were declared under another EU or grants awarded by an EU Member State, non-EU country or other body implementing the EU budget, or they do not comply with the conditions detailed in Articles 6.1 and 6.2, in particular:

- costs related to return on capital and dividends paid by a beneficiary
- debt and debt service charges
- provisions for future losses or debts
- interest owed
- currency exchange losses
- bank costs charged by the beneficiary's bank for transfers from the granting authority
- excessive or reckless expenditure
- deductible or refundable VAT (including VAT paid by public bodies acting as public authority)
- costs incurred or contributions for activities implemented during grant agreement suspension (see Article 31)

4.4 Reporting periods

As specified in Article 21 of the Grant Agreement, the project is divided into three reporting periods of the following duration:

- P1: from month 1 to month 18
- P2: from month 19 to month 30
- P3: from month 31 to month 45

Additional reporting criteria are required for associated partners (UK partners, i.e. FLOW and IRAP). These place reporting requirements to provide quarterly updates to ongoing expenses throughout the project's life. These requirements are in addition to the reporting periods detailed above.

4.5 Deadlines for Periodic Reporting

Reports and deliverables must be submitted to the Project Coordinator according to the timetable shown in Table 6.

Type of document	Submission to PC	Submission to PO
Periodic Activity Report	No later than 30 days after the end of the reporting period	Within 60 days after the end of the reporting period
All other Deliverables	No later than 20 days before the deadlines specified in Annex 1	Within the end of the month indicated in the deliverables list in Annex 1

Table 6 Periodic reporting deadlines

4.6 Files naming

Files should be named according to the example in Table 7 below:

Type of document	Naming
General files in project folders	ProjectAcronym File name Version.Extension Example: PHOEBE Document 0.1.docx
Deliverable files in the WP folders	ProjectAcronym D#.# Deliverable title Version.Extension Example: PHOEBE D7.1 Project Management Handbook 0.1.docx
Deliverable files in the folder “Deliverables”	ProjectAcronym_D1.1 Deliverable title Version.Extension Example: PHOEBE_D7.1 Project Management Handbook 1.0.pdf

Table 7 Naming of files

NOTE:

Version number system 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 etc. Version 1.0 is the final version.

Version 1.0 is the final version getting submitted and will be copied to the Deliverables folder in the root folder.

No version number is required if only one file exists (e.g. for collaborative docs).

4.7 Deliverable preparation procedure

In order to ensure exhaustiveness, clarity and effectiveness, all deliverables shall be made available to the PC for internal reviewing at least 20 days before the deadline indicated in Annex 1. The file has to be sent by e-mail or should be uploaded to the internal repository, and notified the PC. The PC shall revise the document and assess the scientific and technical quality and the editing within six days. In case corrective actions are needed, the PC shall send the document back to the partner in charge of the deliverable, pointing out the corrective actions needed.

The partner shall make the requested amendments and integrations and send the document back to the PC within six days. Then, the PC shall upload the deliverable for feedback in the Google Drive repository, informing the whole consortium via e-mail. Eventual feedback shall be sent to the deliverable responsible (and the PC) within 3 days from notification. The deliverable leader will have 3 days to incorporate eventual feedback and send it back to the Project Coordinator. The Project Coordinator, within two days, shall send the definitive version of the deliverable to the PO and upload the document on the project repository.

The deliverables should be structured according to the template that will be provided by the coordinator and should, among other, include the following information:

- A table, named “Document Control Page” that describes the documentary history and contains the names and surnames of contributors.
- A section, named “Progress beyond the state of the art and play”, that includes a summary of how, why and more precisely to what extent the work reported in the deliverable goes beyond the state of the art and play in its focus area.
- A table summarising the PM effort per beneficiary having contributed to the deliverable.

For the quality assurance of deliverables please refer to Chapter 7.

5 Instructions for exploitation and dissemination

5.1 Internal dissemination

PHOEBE repository on Google Drive will be managed and updated by Shared Drive Manager assigned by iRAP.

In case of any questions, the partners should send an e-mail to Shared Drive Manager (Ms Shanna Lucchesi). All partners have the right to read all pages. To upload or edit documents and files, the partners should add them to the proper folder.

The instructions to use the PHOEBE Repository space and upload area are available below:

- Partners can access the Google shared drive using the invite link sent to partner via email.
- Partners must not share file or folder access externally or provide access links to individuals or organisations that are not part of the PHOEBE consortium.
- Partners have the freedom to upload files and create subfolders as needed. However, the delete function should only be used to delete files created by the individuals. If partners want to delete any file they did not create, they should ask permission from the file owner or the Shared Drive Manager.
- Partners should keep the folders clean and updated. Older versions of documents should be moved to a backup folder that will be created as needed in the subfolder.

iRAP will save a backup of the shared drive via its internal Seafile storage. The backup will be updated with the most recent version of the files on the first Monday of every month. In case partners need older versions of files or have some files accidentally deleted, please contact the shared drive manager.

5.2 Active Accounts

All participants listed in Table 4 have active access to the shared drive.

Important notes

The status of an account will be switched to inactive if the person ceases to work on the PHOEBE project. When a new person joins the PHOEBE project, an account, if needed, will be created. Partners need to inform the PO and Shared Drive Manager of changes in team members.

5.3 Internal communication channels

The project will use video conferencing systems to support the online meeting. EIRA will provide the links to partner access using Microsoft Teams system. Instant messaging, electronic mail and e-mailing lists can be used where necessary. Moreover, the project will hold various physical meetings hosted in turn by Partners. Additional workshops or meetings will be held as required by the work plan and the needs identified by the project. In case of special conditions that do not allow the organisation of physical meetings, online meetings will be planned instead properly.

5.4 PHOEBE mailing lists

The following Table 8 summarises all the current mailing lists created for the PHOEBE project. These lists allow to easily reach all people involved in specific activities or work packages, avoiding missing recipients or multiple sending for a communication.

Mailing list address	E-mail addresses included
phoebe-all@googlegroups.com	All the addresses of the PHOEBE project participants
phoebe-wpleaders@googlegroups.com	The WP leaders
phoebe-wp1@googlegroups.com	The partners involved in WP1
phoebe-wp2@googlegroups.com	The partners involved in WP2
phoebe-wp3@googlegroups.com	The partners involved in WP3
phoebe-wp4@googlegroups.com	The partners involved in WP4
phoebe-wp5@googlegroups.com	The partners involved in WP5
phoebe-wp6@googlegroups.com	The partners involved in WP6
phoebe-wp7@googlegroups.com	The partners involved in WP7
phoebe-dissemination@googlegroups.com	Key people involved in the dissemination activities
phoebe-finance@googlegroups.com	Key people involved in the financial management

Table 8 Current PHOEBE mailing lists

5.5 External dissemination

5.5.1 Public website

The public website address www.phoebe-project.eu and will be used as a repository for all public deliverables, as well as news, events and direct links to partners, sister projects and social media accounts. POLIS Network is responsible for regularly updating the content and relies on content from project partners, especially from the three pilots. The homepage will be created in the months between November and January.

5.5.2 PHOEBE logo

The PHOEBE logo is available to all partners and is saved in a dedicated dissemination material folder in the google shared drive. The logo can only be used for any communication, dissemination and promotion related to the project. The display of the logo should be connected to the disclaimer that includes the project number and funding framework.

5.5.3 PHOEBE e-leaflet

The official PHOEBE e-leaflet will be published on the official PHOEBE homepage 'phoebe-project.eu' in the upcoming months once a clear design has been created through an external agency. However, to avoid too much environmental harm, only a very limited amount of physical flyers will be printed for each partner.

5.5.4 Publication policy

An internal reporting scheme will be created in order to keep track of the official publications. All contributors have to be asked for permission for publication. This includes both WP members as well as members of other WPs and/or contractors who contributed to the results under publication.

The WP leader has to make sure that no material, findings, etc., that cannot be disclosed are published. Only when permission is granted from all the persons involved can the material be published.

The official PHOEBE logo shall be used for conference presentations.

Acknowledgements to the European Commission to be included in all the publications:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101076963. Our Associated Strategic Partners, The International Road Assessment Programme ("iRAP") and The Floop have received grant funding from the UKRI. iRAP has received funding under grant agreement No.10038897 and The Floop under grant agreement 10056912.

Also, the EU Flag will be included in the acknowledgements wherever possible. All publication activities have to be documented in the continuous reporting template on Google Drive to subsequently be used in the periodic report.

Once the material is published, it may be used freely in other publications (or via social media) without another request for permission.

If required, acknowledgements to the UK Research and Innovation will also be included.

5.6 Confidentiality procedure

Three types of documents will be produced according to their dissemination and confidentiality level:

- PU: Public
- RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
- CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

All Partners are strongly invited to write on the front page the confidentiality level of their documents before their release.

The dissemination will be implemented according to the confidentiality level identified by the Intellectual Property Owner/s.

6 Format Specifications for the digital documents and media

In this section, a list of specifications concerning the format of various kinds of documents is provided. Each project participant should try to stick to the standards in use in the project in order to avoid problems during the circulation of documents and other media.

All documents shall be sent to the PC via e-mail or via the repository area in an editable format before submission to the Commission.

Final documents will be in PDF format, especially those that have to be sent to third parties or the Commission.

Concerning the spelling of the project name, even if “PHOEBE” is the official acronym, also “Phoebe” can be used in official documents as well, to reduce misspelling of the name.

British English should be used in all official documents.

6.1 Text documents

All text documents shall preferably be saved using Microsoft Word 2010 format (.docx). All documents edited by several people should activate track changes or at least highlight modified or new text segments. It is important that all modifications are visible and the identity of the person who made the changes is known.

6.2 Presentations

All presentations (slide shows) shall preferably be saved using Microsoft PowerPoint 2010 format (.pptx).

6.3 Tables

All tables and calculations shall preferably be saved using Microsoft Excel 2010 format (.xlsx).

6.4 Images

In general, all images should either use the JPEG or the PNG format. For more complex images, Adobe Photoshop format is suggested.

6.5 Video

In order to minimise size and optimise quality, all videos should be stored using the following video formats: AVI (.avi), WMV (.wmv) or MP4 (.mp4).

7 Quality Assurance Plan

The PC is ultimately responsible for the quality control of the deliverables to the European Commission (EC), coordinating closely with the project SC, the work package and task leaders.

7.1 Peer review

The partners in charge of each deliverable are also responsible for guaranteeing the quality of the project outcome. Each deliverable must be peer-reviewed by representatives of two partners organization. The reviewers will be chosen for each deliverable based on the best combination of expertise (high), involvement in producing the deliverable (low) and availability (high).

Partner responsible for the deliverable should notify the selected reviewers one month in advance. They should agree to participate in the process and the date to receive the materials to review. Reviewers will have one week to send comments and the partner leading the deliverable will have one more week to include comments in the final document. The duration of the two final stages might vary if previously agreed upon partners.

The guiding questions listed below shall be answered in the review process. The list presented below does not intend to extinguish the criteria adopted to ensure delivery quality but serves as a guide of question that needs to be made before delivery.

7.1.1 Format and presentation

- Is the text well written?
- Is it written on the deliverable template?
- Is the information presented clearly and easily understood?
- Are the images relevant to the discussion?
- Does the document follow the project communication guidelines?
- Are all references updated and working?

7.1.2 Content

- Are there significant errors that compromise the interpretation of the results?
- Are the conclusions well-founded?
- Are assumptions (if any) clearly described and realistic?
- Is the document structure clear?
- Did relevant stakeholders review the content?
- Are all the comments addressed or responded?

7.1.3 Accordance with project objectives and goals

- Did the deliverable succeed in achieving its objectives?
- Are the deliverable results suitable for the project's analytical needs?

- Are the contributions by each partner clearly identified and have all, responsible partners contributed to the deliverable?
- If the case, is the deliverable able to clearly demonstrate the technical innovations and the progress beyond state of the art?

8 Annex

List of Deliverables

Deliverable Number & Name		WP	Lead participant	Type	Dissem. level	Date
D1.1	SoA and end user needs review	1	TUD	R	PU	M6
D1.2	Theoretical principles and methodological approach of the PHOEBE framework and selection of tools	1	TUD	R	PU	M12
D2.1	Consolidated data requirements and use case region data availability report	2	FLOWW	R	SEN	M12
D2.2	Data register, feature report and accreditation	2	FLOWW	DATA	PU	M30
D3.1	New and enhanced models/simulation environments and user support materials (Beta ed.)	3	iRAP	OTHER	SEN	M18
D3.2	Finalised models/simulation environments methodology factsheets and user support materials	3	iRAP	R	SEN	M30
D4.1	Use case experimental designs	4	EIRA	R	PU	M12
D4.2	Consolidated use case evaluation and assessment report	4	EIRA	R	PU	M32
D5.1	Consolidated PHOEBE framework methodology, network-level demonstration results and tools	5	NTUA	R	PU	M40
D5.2	User interface and implementation	5	POLIS	R	PU	M44
D6.1	Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan	6	POLIS	R	PU	M4
D6.2	Final exploitation, IPR and replication plans	6	FC	R	SEN	M45
D7.1	Project Management Handbook	7	iRAP	R	PU	M1
D7.2	Data Management Plan (initial version)	7	FLOWW	DMP	PU	M6
D7.3	Data Management Plan (final version)	7	FLOWW	DMP	PU	M45

D7.4	Ethics Management Plan	7	FLOWW	OTHER	PU	M6
------	------------------------	---	-------	-------	----	----

List of Milestones

Milestone Number and Name		Lead beneficiary	WP	Date (month)	Means of verification
MS1	Plan for communication, dissemination and exploitation actions	POLIS	6	M4	Plan for communication, dissemination and exploitation submitted to the EC.
MS2	Methodological framework and technical specifications defined	TUD	1	M12	Theoretical principles, methodological process and technical specifications for the calibration of traffic simulation environments defined.
MS3	Working data available for WP3, WP4 & WP5	FLOWW	2	M18	Processed data meets needs identified in D2.1 and is ready for use case testing.
MS4	Traffic simulation environments prepared for use cases	AIM	3	M18	Aimsun simulations for each use case prepared with encoded behaviour models, data and road safety integration.
MS5	PHOEBE simulation and modelling results validated	iRAP	3	M30	Finalised versions of the models prepared after the completion of the use case demonstrations
MS6	Use case results available for extrapolation to the network-wide level	EIRA	4	M32	Use case simulations performed and results analysed and reviewed by local stakeholders.
MS7	Dynamic road safety assessment models and software released	NTUA	5	M40	Updates to software and tools incorporate enhanced models completed.
MS8	PHOEBE framework user interface launched	POLIS	5	M44	User interface created and user guidelines defined.

